

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTEGRATING FOUR LANGUAGE SKILLS IN LEARNING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Learning and teaching English is the most significant process of present days, it becomes international language over the world and domains in each field such as science, technology, medicine, global trades, economic, media, tourism and etc. This is absolutely widespread among the worldwide workforce. Therefore mastering English requires the four crucial skill; listening, reading, speaking and writing. These basic skills are key and master to learning English. This research paper was coordinated among the school pupils. This study aims to investigate four skills in learning English as a second language of secondary school pupil in Uzbekistan. Four main questions served in study and employed the questionnaire which was organized online using Google platform. According to my research, the majority of pupil's have a positive effect to learning language and they understand four skills are vital in this circumstance.*

Key words: *English, language, learning, skill, listening, reading, speaking, writing.*

Introduction

In contemporary epoch the English has been the ordinary language of the world, it has shown that owing to comprehending of English as a foreign language helps your native language development. In that case indicate the enhancing vocabulary and improved level of literacy all through learning a foreign language. [1]. Learning English as a foreign language which defined EFL course that non-native English learner. It goals to help improves English skill : listening, reading, speaking and writing.

According to Bei Zhang (2013) listening and reading are the process of receiving, speaking and writing are productive process so that is quite arduous for English language learners. In contrast during the practical circumstance four skill work together and help each others to improving, as an example listening procedure helps to develop speaking skill, reading does same to writing skill.[2]

The four skill will encourage the students motivation to fruitfully provoke their language ability. The students get used to learn to speak and write from what they read, see or hear [3]. Brown (2000) assert that fundamental aspect of learning language are listening, reading, speaking and writing that combine together during the use of practical atmosphere [4].

Theoretical basis

Receptive skill	Productive skill
1. Listening	Speaking
2 . Reading	Writing

1. Listening

Listening is one of a substantial portion of the basic language skill. It complex problem-solving skill and it is more than just a perception of sounds. That includes comprehensive of the meaning of clauses, phrases, words, sentence and connected discourse [5]. Hasyuni (2006) said that listening is a creative skill due to we understand the falling upon our ears and take the raw material and arrangement of words, the increase and fall of voice and from that material we creative importance. According to the KH Abdul Chalim and Mojokerto (2021) research listening is a receptive skill and students are able to practice and discussion independently anywhere and anytime[6].

Active and passive are main fraction listening skill and they classify of listening process.

1.1 Active listening

An active listener always attentive in the circumstance of listening process with physically and mentally. Active listening means participation of the listener, good listener who enhance and interest through the message due to he/she has an eye for detail and give a feedback in the contribution and questions. As an example during the lecture students are the active listener and ending of lecture give their own opinion and then debate upon the specific topic. Sympathetic listener is a type of active listener.

1.2 Passive listening

Passive listening is occurred when the listener not require the conversation. In this case listener ordinary hear but not listen and listener becomes apathetic which means faced a arduous topic or loss interest it. That situation is wide range in the classroom atmosphere, subject and topic appear difficult to the students are learned. Hence students feel boring, not interest and listener has a little attention.

2. Reading

Reading is receptive skill which completely meaning are all kind of text. Understanding the reading is academic boost due to it contain location in learning all the subject [7]. Reading is a vital skill both education system and life experiments that it primary life skill because it fundamental step for students' success in education process and throughout life [8]. Despite of importance reading skill, it has a challenging for students. According to the Atkins (1996) a number of students are weak reading ability in English language (L2), this weakness affect to their academic performance that case factor an effective teaching of reading [9]. According to Harmer (2007) there are two main type of reading : Extensive and Intensive;

2.1 Extensive reading

Extensive reading is pleasure activity that students read something belong to their interest. Extensive reading (ER) is approach to L2 reading, when leaner desire to read widely and this circumstance build readers fluence and speed.

2.2 Intensive reading

Intensive reading (IR) focus on specific purpose. For take a test or cram, student has to read grammar, vocabulary and phrases in order to check their reading

comprehension [10]. This type of reading substantial important for learner who learn English as a second language (ESL).

3. Speaking

Speaking is basic productive skill which consist of relating sentence together in the speech context. According to the Chaney (1998) speaking is the art of speaking which owned by person naturally or utilizing productive language skill. Therefore person's skill produce the sound and it understand by others and create good communication. Numerous language learner have a problem with speaking skill due to they afraid to nothing say that means they have a lack of any idea or vocabulary during speaking circumstance. Additionally, ESL student have problem with translation, when they translate word or sentence from mother tongue into English that become a misunderstandable. Bastias (2011) suggest some relevant resolution for that problematic. Initial ESL student make a small debate with easy and clear topics. Then they should make a short speech with three or five sentence relating to the topic. Secondly, they should review essential vocabulary in order to preventing hesitation in the speaking context[11]. Perhaps, that steps can enhance ESL students' speaking skill.

4. Writing

Writing is involves productive skill for second language learners. It more careful use the lexical density, complex words and organize the structure. Good writing quite difficult for ESL student due to need to gathering idea that case we should mind map, before writing essay using a mind map is relevant way for student. Many cases "Repetition" word in the paragraphs which means poor vocabulary [12]. Richard & Renandyah (2002) assert that during the writing generate ideas and organize them to readable text [13].

Method

This study used a questionnaire method to gathering data from the students who learning English as a foreign language. The examination serves evaluate students' language skill such as listening, reading, speaking and writing and which of them easy or arduous for learner or why important that skill for language learners especially ESL. A total of 30 language learners are participant in this study which consist of 20 girls and 10 boys.

Analysis and discussion of finding

The students' respond showed in the graphics which are completed by description.

a. Which skill are you good at?

The graphic shows that forty two whole nine percent of participants have an ability to speaking skill due to they assume that speaking skill is productive skill.

Chaney (1998) claimed that speaking is the art of speaking and mostly it naturally and spontaneous. Again forty two whole nine percent of participants select the reading skill especially extensive reading because it easy to read and it not own theory data, mostly it based on their desire. Bernhardt (1991) assert that the ability to read acknowledged as the most stable and durable of the second language skill (L2). Fourteen whole three percent of participant get an ability to writing skill when they learn second language. If the learner know the structure of writing, maybe it will be easy for them. Unfortunately, according to the questionnaire result listening skill is poor, participants said that they are unable to concentrate and careful during the listening process and they are ordinary hearer.

b. What do you think : listening, reading, speaking and writing skills are important for learning language?

The graphic above indicates that all of the participant agree to this question due to that four skill is significant during the language learning. Listening, reading, speaking and writing components are well developed and widespread among the second language learners so that those are initial step and concept to learning language.

c. Which productive skill easy for you?

This chart shows that speaking skill well conducted by participant rather than writing skill. Sixty percent of participants have an ability to speaking skill because it is more taught than writing and also it conveying a message by spoken language. Additionally, forty percent response choose the writing due to some spoken text or dialog written in the text or book.

d. Which receptive skill easy for you?

From graphic above, fifty seven whole one percent answer is reading skill, forty two whole nine percent response is listening skill. According to the questionnaire result reading is easy for big fraction of participant due to it is information text, getting new knowledge when you read the book or someone can relax during reading story. Listing also easy for small part of participant because you must careful and focus on something during the listening process and sometimes pronunciation is problem for listening circumstance so that you are unable to understand it.

Conclusion

The current research paper has discussed and demonstrated the importance of four different skill in learning English as a foreign language. Listening and reading are the receptive skill, speaking and writing are the productive skill, however four foundational skill combine together while mastering language. Consequently, language learners are eager to comprehend a basic skills, accomplish the language proficiency in near the future.

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